

Epistemic Justice Indicator: An Annotated Prototype

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Authors:

Hernán Bobadilla, Department of Mathematics, Politecnico di Milano. La Nave, Via Edoardo Bonardi 9, 20133 Milano, Italy. ORCID: 0000-0003-0003-9952.

Corresponding author: hernanfelipe.bobadilla@polimi.it

Giuseppe Di Capua, Italian Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology. Via di Vigna Murata 605, 00143 Roma, Italy. ORCID: 0000-0002-1254-3200

Chris Hesselbein, Department of Management Engineering, Politecnico di Milano. Via Raffaele Lambruschini 4C, 20156 Milano, Italy. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4258-6671

Silvia Peppoloni, Italian Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology. Via di Vigna Murata 605, 00143 Roma, Italy. ORCID: 0000-0002-2667-6506

Federico Lampis*, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission. Square Frère-Orban 8, 1000 Bruxelles, Belgium.

**The information and views set out in this document are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Commission.*

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Preliminaries

I. Notes on the indicator's design

We introduce a **prototype** of an **indicator for epistemic justice**. The indicator is designed as a **process indicator**, i.e., it evaluates justice in policymaking processes (mechanisms and overall efforts) rather than their outcomes. It is structured as a **checklist** with **two main categories**: i) relative to the **legislative phase** of policymaking, and ii) relative to the **dimension of epistemic justice**. We distinguish between **two legislative phases** of policymaking, namely **ex-ante** (i.e., problem framing) and **ex-post** (i.e., appraisal of the policy's initial design). We also distinguish three dimensions of epistemic justice, namely **recognitional, participatory, and distributive**. As a result of combining these categories, the indicator has **six distinct sections**. In each section, relevant questions are asked for assessment and scoring, which were developed based on our combined field experiences and literature reviews. The indicator has a total of **23 questions**. Each question calls for a quantitative evaluation, using a **scoring system** on a scale **from 1 to 10**. The sum of points across questions in a specific section results in a **section score**. The **global score** is the sum of points across all sections. Depending on their specific aims, policymakers may prefer to aggregate the scores of specific sections (e.g., ex-ante sections). We assume that **local knowledge** is a key component in advancing more effective and just policymaking, especially in the field of climate adaptation (for more details, see our chapter in the SSH Climate book). Hence, our scoring system is designed to give more prominence to local stakeholders in the policymaking process. The standardised scoring system enables **tractability** and **accountability**.¹

¹ Since this is a prototype, we expect to further improve the design of this indicator as we test it in different contexts and with different audiences. For the most recent version, please write to the corresponding author.

II. Notes on technocracy, bureaucracy, and democracy

To score a significant proportion of the questions (especially in the ex-ante stage), we have distinguished between technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means for advancing epistemic justice. We articulate this threefold distinction in general terms. **Technocratic means** refer to the contents of (peer-reviewed) academic literature and the opinions of well-established experts in pertinent fields. **Bureaucratic means** refer to the instruments, procedures, and protocols developed and/or managed by widely legitimised institutions, organisations, and agencies, both public and private. A key example is the European Commission’s ‘Better Regulation Toolbox’ document. **Democratic means** refer to the various initiatives developed and/or managed by various stakeholders. A host of examples have been collected during research across the globe, which include (but are not limited to): citizen committees, citizen juries, deliberative opinion polls, focus groups, information repositories, fishbowl discussions, interviews with key stakeholders, workshops, study circles, and role plays.

III. Notes on implementation

The indicator is a tool that focuses on specific dimensions for standardised evaluation by providing guidelines for their scoring. As a tool, the indicator is directed towards policymakers who are in a strong position to conduct the evaluation. However, a scoring provided only by policymakers is likely to be biased in various, predictable ways. To overcome such scoring biases, we recommended crowdsourcing the indicator: The more evaluations informing a score, the less biased it will ultimately be. In this sense, the implementation of the indicator falls within a range: from a score provided by one or a few policymakers to a score that takes into account various evaluations from various stakeholders (e.g., via perception survey data). Ultimately, the implementation of the indicator will depend on various contextual, infrastructural, and cultural factors.

IV. Notes on the European Commission’s “Better Regulation” Toolbox

The European Commission’s ‘Better Regulation’ Toolbox is an extensive document containing crucial guidelines for policymaking. This toolbox advances epistemic justice in various regards, even if implicitly, and we regard it as a step in the right direction. Still, we suggest that our indicator may assist in the implementation of several of these tools by drawing explicit attention to dimensions of epistemic justice in policymaking. We illustrate some gaps in the Toolbox in terms of its focus (or lack thereof) on epistemic justice with a few examples:

- **Stakeholder consultation** is the topic of Chapter 7 (tools #51 to #55). The chapter focuses on the ex-post stage, making stakeholders’ consultation tantamount to stakeholders’ validation of a proposed policy. More explicitly, stakeholders and the public are invited to ‘give their feedback on the “call for evidence” document, which explains *the Commission’s understanding of the problem* and possible solutions’ (445, *our emphasis*). In other chapters, the Toolbox discusses stakeholders’ participation in earlier stages of policymaking. However, by using the notion of “stakeholders’ consultation” to label mostly ex-post activities, we suggest that stakeholder participation is (maybe inadvertently) partly excluded from problem framing. Tool #54 (“Analysing data and informing policymaking”) deserves special attention, as it includes a “stakeholder credibility test” (p. 482). We estimate that some of the criteria to assess stakeholders’ credibility are questionable from an epistemic justice

perspective, especially presented as general considerations that could lead to stereotypes. For example: i) longevity is taken as a proxy for wisdom in a field. However, longevity as a marker of credibility risks promoting a prejudiced outlook towards testimonies coming from younger stakeholders and their newly formed organizations; ii) expertise is taken as a criterion for credibility. However, “expertise” is not explained (how is it attributed to stakeholders?). In addition, a focus on expertise as a marker of credibility risks promoting a prejudiced outlook towards non-expert testimonies; iii) reputation (i.e., how serious a stakeholder is taken by other people) is a disputable criterion for credibility, especially with an outlook towards recognitional and participatory epistemic justice: Marginalized perspectives are often not taken seriously, which does not mean that they are undeserving of credibility.

- A clearer focus on the ex-ante stage is found in Chapter 3: ‘**Identifying Impacts in Evaluations, Fitness Checks and Impact Assessments**’ (especially important to our aims is tool #34, focused on territorial impacts). However, we suggest that there are aspects in which the tools of this chapter are not open enough to accommodate democratic means for stakeholder participation. For example, tool #18 (identification of impacts) presents a table with an ‘overview of key impacts to screen’. While helpful for reducing the plurality (and complexity) of impacts, this table nevertheless sets an agenda in terms of the impacts that deserve central attention. Furthermore, the impacts are conceptualised in specific ways that may not be in agreement with the interpretations of other stakeholders. For example, climate is characterised as an environmental impact, whereas the impact experienced by stakeholders may be best characterised as economic or social (139).
- Tool #4 (**evidence-based policymaking**) is worth discussing in some detail. This tool focuses on the need for reliable evidence in policymaking processes. However, its conceptualisation is predominantly technocratic and bureaucratic while democratic means are barely discussed. For example:
 - i*) in discussing the broadening of perspectives on the problems at hand, there is no explicit mention of a diversity of stakeholder perspectives: Broadening is mainly characterized as a ‘forward-looking’ attitude (22);
 - ii*) in addressing ‘what does success look like?’, the discussion focuses on establishing measurable targets. However, stakeholders’ views on what success looks like may not lead to quantifiable standards. Such views nevertheless need to inform any criteria for success (22-3);
 - iii*) in discussing evidence from mapping exercises, the focus is strictly on internal (i.e., bureaucratic) and external (i.e., technocratic) expertise. Stakeholders’ feedback is discussed exclusively in the context of the ‘Have Your Say’ consultation portal, but this portal collects feedback solely on ‘existing’ initiatives. This means that initiatives can be modified only at a later stage, thus excluding the possibility of a cooperative framing of problems from their inception (23);
 - iv*) the technocratic inclination is also evident in the call for collecting evidence by ‘drawing on knowledge and expertise from several disciplines’. These recommendations make no explicit mention of non-disciplinary local practices, experiences, and knowledges (24);
 - v*) in discussing sources of evidence, most of the space is dedicated to technocratic and bureaucratic sources (e.g., data and statistics from different institutions, commission services, official reports, and experts of various sorts, p. 27-9). Stakeholders are briefly mentioned at the end of the section (p. 29) for their capacity to submit information (data and lessons from implementation). However, no explicit mention is made of their specific capacity to frame problems in a different or

complementary manner. Indeed, stakeholders are the only source of evidence whose reliability is explicitly questioned: ‘When using evidence gathered through consultation one should bear in mind the specific interest of stakeholders providing the information and try to validate the robustness of the results. Peer-reviewing or benchmarking with other surveys/studies or consultation activities can significantly enhance the quality of such information’ (29).

Checklist

I. *Ex-ante recognitional*

1) Identification of stakeholders

To what extent have efforts to identify and accurately represent collective and individual relevant stakeholders – i.e., those potentially affected by the forthcoming policy – been conducted? And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by these stakeholders?

To advance recognitional epistemic justice, collective and individual stakeholders potentially affected by the forthcoming policy must be identified *before* the policy is designed (for inclusion in problem framing). Identification of stakeholders can be conducted via i) technocratic means, i.e., evidence collected through literature reviews in relevant disciplines and testimony of experts (e.g., data published in scientific peer-reviewed papers); ii) bureaucratic means, i.e., evidence collected through engagement with formal local institutions, both public and private (e.g., Territorial Impact Assessment or TIAs); iii) democratic means, i.e., evidence collected through crowdsourcing and various engagement initiatives with non-formal, citizen/inhabitant/stakeholder collectives (e.g., forums and citizen committees).

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to identify relevant stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to identify relevant stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to identify relevant stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to identify relevant stakeholders.

2) Identification of relations

To what extent have efforts to identify and accurately represent the relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts been conducted? And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by the stakeholders?

To advance recognitional epistemic justice, relations among stakeholders need to be recognized *before* the policy is designed (for problem framing). In particular, social arrangements and power dynamics need to be specified. In addition, relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts need to be identified, such as their relations to ecosystems, land, and natural resources. Identification of relations can be conducted via i) technocratic means, i.e., evidence collected through literature reviews in relevant disciplines and testimony of experts (e.g., data published in scientific peer-reviewed papers); ii) bureaucratic means, i.e., evidence collected through

engagement with formal local institutions, both public and private (e.g., Territorial Impact Assessment or TIAs); iii) democratic means, i.e., evidence collected through crowdsourcing and various engagement initiatives with non-formal, citizen/inhabitant/stakeholder collectives (e.g., workshops and citizen committees).

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to identify relevant relations among stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to identify relevant relations among stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to identify relevant relations among stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to identify relevant relations among stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts.

3) Identification of conflicts

To what extent have efforts to identify and accurately represent conflicts between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts been conducted? And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by the stakeholders?

To advance recognitional epistemic justice, an identification of conflicts among stakeholders needs to be conducted *before* the policy is designed (for problem framing). Conflicts may involve differences in values, knowledges, resources, power differentials, interests, and needs. Both historical and ongoing conflicts must be identified. The identification of conflicts can be conducted via i) technocratic means, i.e., evidence collected through literature reviews in relevant disciplines and testimony of experts (e.g., data published in scientific peer-reviewed papers); ii) bureaucratic means, i.e., evidence collected through engagement with formal local institutions, both public and private (e.g., Territorial Impact Assessment or TIAs); iii) democratic means, i.e., evidence collected through crowdsourcing and various engagement initiatives with non-formal, citizen/inhabitant/stakeholder collectives (e.g., workshops and citizen committees).

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to identify relevant conflicts between stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to identify relevant conflicts between stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to identify relevant conflicts between stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to identify relevant conflicts between stakeholders.

4) Identification of uncertainties

To what extent have efforts to identify and accurately represent uncertainties been conducted? And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by the stakeholders?

To advance recognitional epistemic justice, uncertainties affecting stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts must be recognized *before* the policy is

designed (for problem framing). In particular, vulnerabilities and exposure to hazards need to be surveyed. The identification of uncertainties can be conducted via i) technocratic means, i.e., evidence collected through literature reviews in relevant disciplines and testimony of experts (e.g., data published in scientific peer-reviewed papers); ii) bureaucratic means, i.e., evidence collected through engagement with formal local institutions, both public and private (e.g., Territorial Impact Assessment or TIAs); iii) democratic means, i.e., evidence collected through crowdsourcing and various engagement initiatives with non-formal, citizen/inhabitant/stakeholder collectives (e.g., workshops and citizen committees).

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to identify uncertainties affecting stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to identify uncertainties affecting stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to identify uncertainties affecting stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to identify uncertainties affecting stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts.

5) Synthetic integration

To what extent have efforts to synthesise and integrate standpoints been conducted?
And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by the stakeholders?

To move beyond the ex-ante stage, a synthesis should be reached that integrates the views of the various stakeholders. Standpoints must not be merely aggregated but actively integrated in ways that lead to policies that may be collectively supported. Synthetic integration can be conducted based on i) technocratic means, i.e., theoretical frameworks in the literature or expert opinions (e.g., using concepts and taxonomies specific to disciplines and research programs in the social sciences); ii) bureaucratic means, i.e., established protocols, procedures, and mechanisms managed by institutions, both public and private; iii) democratic means, i.e., crowdsourced procedures with engaged stakeholders.

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to synthetically integrate the standpoints of the various stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to synthetically integrate the standpoints of the various stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to synthetically integrate the standpoints of the various stakeholders. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to synthetically integrate the standpoints of the various stakeholders.

II. *Ex-ante participatory*

6) Mobilisation

To what extent are mechanisms in place for free and full articulation as well as sharing of stakeholders' knowledges and experiences? And to what extent are these mechanisms designed/implemented by stakeholders themselves?

To advance participatory epistemic justice, stakeholders' knowledges and experiences need to be mobilised - i.e., articulated in ways that enable sharing - using culturally appropriate methods (cf. Tengö et al. 2021, Malmer et al. 2020). Mobilisation presumes that stakeholders can autonomously engage with and produce epistemic systems using internal validation processes. The knowledges produced through these validation processes need to be articulated in a manner that allows for sharing across different epistemic systems. Mobilisation can be conducted via i) technocratic mechanisms, based on literature findings and/or managed by experts, ii) bureaucratic mechanisms, based on formal procedures channelled and supervised by established institutions, and iii) democratic mechanisms, based on stakeholders' initiatives and considerations.

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic mechanisms have been deployed to mobilise stakeholders' knowledges. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to mobilise stakeholders' knowledges. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to mobilise stakeholders' knowledges. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to mobilise stakeholders' knowledges.

7) Intertranslation

To what extent are mechanisms in place for the translation of various knowledges? And to what extent are these mechanisms designed/implemented by stakeholders?

To advance participatory epistemic justice, stakeholders' knowledges need to be mutually comprehensible. This mutual understanding includes (but is not limited to) inter-intelligible languages, terminologies, cosmologies, and ontologies. Intertranslation is typically achieved through iterative processes of communication among various stakeholders and organisations. A key marker of successful intertranslation is jointly produced outcomes, e.g., maps or conceptual frameworks (Tengö et al. 2017). Intertranslation can be conducted via i) technocratic mechanisms, based on literature findings and/or managed by experts, ii) bureaucratic mechanisms, based on formal procedures channelled and supervised by established institutions, and iii) democratic mechanisms, based on stakeholders' initiatives and considerations.

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic mechanisms have been deployed to translate stakeholders' knowledges. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to translate stakeholders' knowledges. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to translate stakeholders' knowledges. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to translate stakeholders' knowledges.

8) Dialogue and negotiations

To what extent are the conditions for horizontal dialogues and transparent negotiations in place? And to what extent are these conditions curated and managed by relevant stakeholders?

To advance participatory epistemic justice, horizontal dialogues and transparent negotiations are required. Dialogues involve reciprocal listening, questioning, engaged responses, and assertions. Negotiations involve respectful interactions and the transparent communication of needs, interests, and expectations, to develop useful representations of knowledge (Tengö et al. 2017). These dialogues and negotiations acknowledge important differences between stakeholders and epistemic systems. However, common ground needs to be found to move towards the development of a public policy (which is going to affect stakeholders in a broad public space). This common ground does not need to be conceptualised as a ‘consensus’ or ‘average’. Instead, interactive integration of viewpoints may be more effective, which represents the ideas or positions that all stakeholders are willing to endorse by being involved in their development. The conditions for dialogue and negotiation may be advanced through i) technocratic means, based on literature findings and/or managed by experts, ii) bureaucratic means, based on formal procedures channelled and supervised by established institutions, and iii) democratic means, based on stakeholders’ considerations.

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to advance conditions for dialogue and negotiations. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to advance conditions for dialogue and negotiations. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to advance conditions for dialogue and negotiations. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to advance conditions for dialogue and negotiations.

9) Application

To what extent are mechanisms in place for the effective uptake of stakeholders’ knowledge in policymaking? And to what extent are these mechanisms designed/implemented by stakeholders?

To advance participatory epistemic justice, stakeholders’ ex-ante contributions need to become part of (or at least inform) the content of ensuing policies. This requires mechanisms to secure the effective uptake of such contributions. The effective uptake of stakeholders’ knowledge may be fostered through i) technocratic mechanisms, based on literature findings and/or managed by experts, ii) bureaucratic mechanisms, based on formal procedures channelled and supervised by established institutions, and iii) democratic mechanisms, based on stakeholders’ considerations.

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to advance conditions for dialogue and negotiations. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to advance conditions for dialogue and negotiations. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to advance conditions for dialogue and negotiations. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to advance conditions for dialogue and negotiations.

10) Testimonial injustice (ex-ante)

To what extent are mechanisms to prevent (and/or repair) testimonial injustices in place? And to what extent are these mechanisms designed/implemented by stakeholders?

To advance participatory epistemic justice, there must be an unprejudiced uptake of testimonies. Socio-cultural and personal biases can be reduced with appropriate mechanisms that promote and secure stakeholders' participation, thus empowering them as contributors and preparing them as listeners. Testimonial injustices are susceptible to occurring in all previous aspects of participation, i.e., mobilisation, intertranslation, dialogue, negotiations, and application. Testimonial justice can be advanced through i) technocratic mechanisms, based on literature findings and/or managed by experts (e.g., professional facilitators and mediators), ii) bureaucratic mechanisms, based on formal procedures channelled and supervised by established institutions (e.g., binding quotas), and iii) democratic mechanisms, based on stakeholders' considerations (e.g., citizen juries and fishbowl discussions).

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to prevent (and/or repair) testimonial injustices. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to prevent (and/or repair) testimonial injustices. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to prevent (and/or repair) testimonial injustices. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to prevent (and/or repair) testimonial injustices.

11) Hermeneutical injustice (ex-ante)

To what extent are mechanisms to prevent (and/or repair) hermeneutical injustices in place? And to what extent are these mechanisms designed/implemented by stakeholders?

To advance participatory epistemic justice, hermeneutical injustices need to be reduced. Hermeneutical injustices occur whenever speakers are unable to render their experiences and perspectives intelligible, either to themselves or to others. This can happen due to systemic discrimination, which can prevent groups from establishing or even finding suitable means for interpreting their experiences of injustice (Fricker 2007). The systemic nature of such injustices makes them difficult to overcome in the context of a policymaking process. However, hermeneutic justice could be improved through i) technocratic means, based on literature findings and/or expert opinions (e.g., identifying potentially relevant hermeneutical injustices in similar contexts discussed in the literature), ii) bureaucratic means, based on formal procedures channelled and supervised by established institutions (e.g., 'better regulation' practices), and iii) democratic

mechanisms, based on stakeholders' considerations (e.g., integration through stakeholders' initiatives).

[10–8] Technocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic means have been deployed to prevent (and/or repair) hermeneutical injustices. Score higher if democratic means are most significant.

[7–5] Only two of three kinds of means have been deployed to prevent (and/or repair) hermeneutical injustices. Score higher if democratic means are used and are most significant.

[4–2] Only one of three kinds of means has been deployed to prevent (and/or repair) hermeneutical injustices. Score higher if democratic means are used.

[1] No means have been deployed to prevent (and/or repair) hermeneutical injustices.

III. Ex-ante distributive

12) Epistemic resources (ex-ante)

To what extent are mechanisms in place to promote the fair distribution of epistemic resources relevant to the policymaking process in the ex-ante stage? And to what extent does this distribution aid local communities?

To advance distributive epistemic justice, epistemic resources need to be fairly distributed among stakeholders. Epistemic resources are objects or practices that contain (or are conducive to) data, information, and knowledge. As a process indicator, the scoring system does not reflect the fair distribution of resources (i.e., an outcome), but instead the implementation of mechanisms that promote fair distribution. Given our preference for a 'prioritarian' principle, a higher score is given when mechanisms promote egalitarian distributions that deviate from the principle of equity only to benefit local communities. We take local management of these mechanisms as a proxy for justifying such a deviation. Mechanisms to advance a fair distribution of epistemic resources may be infrastructural (e.g., open access to repositories, libraries, and media) or programmatic (e.g., dissemination events, exhibitions, and forums). These mechanisms may be managed bureaucratically, i.e., by formal institutions, or democratically, i.e., by stakeholders.

[10-8] There are infrastructural and programmatic mechanisms in place that promote a fair distribution of epistemic resources, mostly managed by local stakeholders. Score higher the more influence local stakeholders have in the management of these mechanisms.

[7-5] There are infrastructural and programmatic mechanisms that promote a fair distribution of epistemic resources, mostly managed bureaucratically. Score higher if local stakeholders have more influence in the management of these mechanisms.

[4-2] There are either infrastructural or programmatic mechanisms that promote a fair distribution of epistemic resources. Score higher if most of these mechanisms are managed by local stakeholders' collectives.

[1] There are no mechanisms in place that promote a fair distribution of epistemic resources.

13) Epistemic capabilities (ex-ante)

To what extent are mechanisms in place to promote the fair distribution of epistemic capabilities relevant to the policymaking process in the ex-ante stage? And to what extent does this distribution aid local communities?

To advance distributive epistemic justice, epistemic capabilities need to be fairly distributed among stakeholders. Epistemic capabilities are substantial freedoms that stakeholders possess to pursue ends that they value in the epistemic arena. As an illustration, epistemic capabilities include (but are not limited to) the ability to search and acquire information and knowledge, avoid false beliefs, make epistemic contributions, gain credibility, and learn specific methodologies. Individuals may be differently able to convert epistemic resources into actions that advance their epistemic ends. This is why a focus on capabilities is required to complement the assessment of the distribution of resources. Given our preference for a ‘prioritarian’ principle, a higher score is given when mechanisms promote egalitarian distributions that deviate from the principle of equity only to benefit local communities. We take local management of these mechanisms as a proxy for such deviation. Mechanisms to advance a fair distribution of epistemic capabilities may be infrastructural (e.g., free access to repositories, libraries, and media) or programmatic (e.g., dissemination events, exhibitions, and forums). These mechanisms may be managed bureaucratically, i.e., by formal institutions, or democratically, i.e., by stakeholders.

[10-8] There are infrastructural and programmatic mechanisms in place that promote a fair distribution of epistemic capabilities, mostly managed by local stakeholders. Score higher the more influence local stakeholders have in the management of these mechanisms.

[7-5] There are infrastructural and programmatic mechanisms that promote a fair distribution of epistemic capabilities, mostly managed bureaucratically. Score higher if local stakeholders have more influence in the management of these mechanisms.

[4-2] There are either infrastructural or programmatic mechanisms that promote a fair distribution of epistemic capabilities. Score higher if most of these mechanisms are managed by local stakeholders’ collectives.

[1] There are no mechanisms in place that promote a fair distribution of epistemic capabilities.

IV. Ex-post recognitional

14) Addressing stakeholders

To what extent have efforts been made to identify and acknowledge the collective and individual stakeholders relevant to the ensuing policy (or policies)? And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by the stakeholders?

To advance recognitional epistemic justice, the resulting policy must recognize and address the relevant stakeholders. That is, the content of the policy must make explicit or implicit reference to the local stakeholders. This assessment relies on the information collected during the ex-ante identification stage. If there is no ex-ante identification of stakeholders, the policymaking process will be ill-informed. The quality of the ex-ante identification in terms of advancing recognitional epistemic justice is already evaluated in question [1].

[10–8] There is ex-ante identification of stakeholders. Over 75% of these stakeholders are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher if more stakeholders are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise representation in the policy.

[7-5] There is ex-ante identification of stakeholders. Between 50% and 75% of these stakeholders are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher if more stakeholders are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise representation in the policy.

[4-2] There is ex-ante identification of stakeholders. Below 50% of these stakeholders are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher if more stakeholders are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise representation in the policy.

[1] There is no ex-ante identification of stakeholders.

15) Addressing relations

To what extent have efforts been made to address the relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts in the ensuing policy (or policies)? And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by the stakeholders?

To advance recognitional epistemic justice, the resulting policy must recognize and address the relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. That is, the content of the policy must make explicit or implicit reference to these relations. This assessment relies on the information collected during the ex-ante identification stage. If there is no ex-ante identification of relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts, the policymaking process will be ill-informed. The quality of the ex-ante identification in terms of advancing recognitional epistemic justice is already evaluated in question [2].

[10–8] There is ex-ante identification of relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Over 75% of these relations are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more relations are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of relations.

[7-5] There is ex-ante identification of relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Between 50% and 75% of these relations are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more relations are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of relations.

[4-2] There is ex-ante identification of relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Below 50% of these relations are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more relations are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of relations.

[1] There is no ex-ante identification of relations between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts.

16) Addressing conflicts

To what extent have efforts been made to address the potential conflicts between stakeholders in the ensuing policy (or policies)? And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by the stakeholders?

To advance recognitional epistemic justice, the resulting policy must recognize and address potential conflicts between stakeholders. That is, the content of the policy must make explicit or implicit reference to such potential conflicts. This assessment relies on

the information collected during the ex-ante identification stage. If there is no ex-ante identification of conflicts between stakeholders, the policymaking process will be ill-informed. The quality of the ex-ante identification in terms of advancing recognitional epistemic justice is already evaluated in question [3].

[10–8] There is ex-ante identification of conflicts between stakeholders. Over 75% of these conflicts are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more conflicts are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of conflicts.

[7-5] There is ex-ante identification of conflicts between stakeholders. Between 50% and 75% of these conflicts are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more conflicts are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of conflicts.

[4-2] There is ex-ante identification of conflicts between stakeholders. Below 50% of these conflicts are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more conflicts are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of conflicts.

[1] There is no ex-ante identification of conflicts between stakeholders.

17) Addressing uncertainties

To what extent have efforts been made to address potential uncertainties affecting the stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts in the ensuing policy (or policies)? And to what extent are these efforts legitimised by the stakeholders?

To advance recognitional epistemic justice, the resulting policy must recognize and address the various potential uncertainties affecting the stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. That is, the content of the policy must make explicit or implicit reference to these potential uncertainties. This assessment relies on the information collected in the ex-ante identification stage. If there is no ex-ante identification of uncertainties, the policymaking process will be ill-informed. The quality of the ex-ante identification in terms of advancing recognitional epistemic justice is already evaluated in question [4].

[10–8] There is ex-ante identification of uncertainties affecting the stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Over 75% of these uncertainties are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more uncertainties are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of uncertainties.

[7-5] There is ex-ante identification of uncertainties affecting the stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Between 50% and 75% of these uncertainties are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more uncertainties are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of uncertainties.

[4-2] There is ex-ante identification of uncertainties between stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts. Below 50% of these uncertainties are addressed in the policy (or policies). Score higher the more uncertainties are addressed. Score higher if there are democratic mechanisms in place that legitimise recognition of uncertainties.

[1] There is no ex-ante identification of uncertainties affecting the stakeholders and their environmental and socio-economic contexts.

18) The rationale for excluding views

To what extent does the synopsis report published at the end of consultation activities inform stakeholders on how their input has been considered? In what manner does it explain and justify why certain suggestions have not been taken up?

Transparent communication on why specific views have not been taken up during the policymaking process is important for ascertaining whether recognitional epistemic injustices have been reinforced while preparing an initiative. Tool #54 in the Better Regulation Toolbox mandates the preparation of a synopsis report at the end of consultation activities to ‘inform policymaking on the outcome of [...] activities’ and to ‘inform stakeholders on how their input has been considered and to explain why certain suggestions could not be taken up’. This item of our indicator complements Tool #54 and should help with evaluating its implementation.

[10–8] The synopsis report informs stakeholders on which and how input was considered and provides a detailed explanation about why specific input was not taken up. Score higher the more detailed the explanation.

[7–5] The synopsis report informs stakeholders on which and how input was considered; it acknowledges the discarding of specific input but does not provide a detailed explanation as to the rationale behind the decision to do so.

[4–2] The synopsis report informs stakeholders on which and how input was considered; it does not acknowledge the discarding of specific input.

[1] The synopsis report does not provide sufficient information to stakeholders and does not acknowledge the discarding of a specific input.

V. Ex-post participatory

19) Reach of participatory mechanisms

To what extent have calls for evidence as well as public consultation documents reached stakeholders that may be impacted by the policy, especially considering stakeholders previously identified by policymakers in the ex-ante (i.e., problem-framing) phase?²

During the preparation of a legislative initiative’s draft, the European Commission gives the public the opportunity to provide input via the online ‘Have Your Say’ platform. For input to be as meaningful as possible, stakeholders affected by the policy should be able to share their views. Although the online platform is openly accessible, it is unrealistic to assume that all relevant stakeholders will contribute their views. Collective and individual stakeholders may be experiencing structural limitations that may be preventing them from contributing their views through the platform. In a similar vein, it is not feasible to know which stakeholders have been reached by calls for evidence and public consultation documents and have nevertheless decided not to share their views. Nonetheless, the level of reach can be verified, or at least approximated, by comparing

² Stakeholders may have a hard time evaluating this and similar points of the checklist assuming they do not have access to the ex-ante identification outcomes performed by policymakers (if they exist). Still, stakeholders may evaluate this and similar points by checking responses to consultations against their own mappings.

the alignment of stakeholders that have responded with the stakeholders that have been identified in the ex-ante phase. Higher alignment indicates a broader reach, and therefore a more satisfactory degree of participatory justice. The scoring system also considers the representativeness of the pool of respondents to detect biases towards specific interests or views. Having non-diverse responses may indicate that certain sectors of society have not been reached via consultation activities.

[10–8] Complete or almost complete alignment of respondents with stakeholders identified in the ex-ante phase (over 90%).

[7–5] Respondents are a representative pool of the stakeholders identified in the ex-ante phase with a satisfactory distribution across different segments of society (civil society, NGOs, businesses, etc.), suggesting a sufficient diversity of views in responses (60–90%).

[4–2] Respondents are a non-representative pool of the stakeholders identified in the ex-ante phase (below 60%), with an unsatisfactory distribution across different segments of society (civil society, NGOs, businesses, etc.), suggesting an insufficient diversity of views in responses.

[1] Low number of respondents, suggesting an absence of diversity of views.

20) Testimonial injustice (ex-post)

To what extent do participatory mechanisms rely on stereotypes? And to what extent are these mechanisms designed/implemented/informed by stakeholders?

To advance participatory epistemic justice, there must be an unprejudiced uptake of various testimonies in the ex-post stage. Socio-cultural and personal biases can be mitigated with appropriate mechanisms that promote and secure effective participation by stakeholders. Such mechanisms need to prevent/correct stereotypes that might affect credibility (cf. Fricker 2007, 30). The ‘Have Your Say’ platform is a key target here, as it functions as the European Commission’s official channel for stakeholder consultation in the ex-post stage. The ‘stakeholder credibility test’ (see Tool #54 in Better Regulation Toolbox) arguably does not meet the right standards for securing testimonial justice during stakeholder consultations for the reasons discussed above (see Preliminaries IV): It relies on stereotypical heuristics to assign credibility. Two additional considerations are worth mentioning here. First, the ‘stakeholder credibility test’ is mostly expressed in terms of stakeholders’ organizations. Views submitted as input to calls for evidence or public consultations by individual citizens should not be held in lower regard if these individuals are not part of a larger group or organisation. Second, testimonies that include affective responses may be considered less credible. However, as Preston and Carr (2018) claim: “Affective responses can provide a clue about whether a policy meets the conditions of recognitional justice”. Thus, attention and fair treatment to affective responses are required for testimonial justice.

[10-8] Participatory mechanisms do not rely on stereotypes as a heuristic to evaluate credibility. Score higher if mechanisms are designed/implemented/informed by stakeholders.

[7-5] Participatory mechanisms rely on stereotypes as a heuristic to evaluate credibility. However, these stereotypes are democratically legitimised by local stakeholders. Score higher the more local stakeholders inform the design of these mechanisms.

[4-2] Participatory mechanisms rely on stereotypes as a heuristic to evaluate credibility. These stereotypes are mostly based on bureaucratic standards, i.e., not democratically

informed. Score higher the more channels local stakeholders have to provide feedback to these mechanisms.

[1] There are no participatory mechanisms.

21) Hermeneutical injustice (ex-post)

To what extent can stakeholders meaningfully provide their input to public consultations in a manner that is in line with their knowledge systems and experiences? To what extent have public consultation documents been designed with different knowledge systems in mind? And to what extent are these mechanisms designed/implemented by stakeholders?

To advance participatory epistemic justice, stakeholders should have an equal opportunity to partake in consultation activities. This includes the possibility for stakeholders to participate in a manner that reflects their knowledge systems. As a proxy for hermeneutical injustice, the scoring measures the requirement to provide technical information that can be reasonably expected to only be shared by stakeholders that would be traditionally considered scientific or technical experts, e.g. academics or staff within a company active in the areas impacted by a policy. If more technical information is requested from non-traditional experts, consultation activities may be less suitable for different knowledge systems. In addition, this item measures the size and representativeness of the pool of respondents to consultation activities (responses coming from different sectors of society can indicate that consultation activities are suited for more knowledge systems).

[10–8] Public consultation documents include several open questions that do not require the provision of technical information that can be reasonably expected to only be shared by experts; input received via the public consultation comes from a wide pool of respondents (including non-experts) that can be considered representative of the stakeholders identified in the ex-ante phase.

[7–5] Public consultation documents include some open questions that do not require the provision of technical information that can be reasonably expected to only be shared by experts; input received via the public consultation includes some non-expert responses.

[4–2] Public consultation documents include some open questions that do not require the provision of technical information that can be reasonably expected to only be shared by experts; input received via the public consultation is skewed towards expert responses only.

[1] Public consultation documents only include questions that require the provision of technical information that can be reasonably expected to only be shared by experts; input received via the public consultation only includes expert responses.

VI. *Ex-post distributive*

22) Epistemic resources (ex-post)

To what extent does the proposed policy advance fairer distributions of epistemic resources? And to what extent does this distribution aid local communities?

To advance distributive epistemic justice, epistemic resources need to be fairly distributed among stakeholders. Epistemic resources are objects or practices that contain (or are conducive to) data, information, and knowledge. As a process indicator, the scoring system does not evaluate the effects of the policy on the distribution of epistemic

resources (that would make it an outcome indicator). Instead, the scoring is based on how the preliminary design of the policy, either explicitly or implicitly, addresses issues of distribution of epistemic resources. Given our preference for a ‘prioritarian’ principle, a higher score is given when the policy describes distributive means that promote egalitarian distributions that deviate from the principle of equity only to benefit local communities. We take local management of these means as a proxy for justifying such a deviation. The policy may advance a fairer distribution of epistemic resources by infrastructural (e.g., open access to repositories, libraries, and media) or programmatic (e.g., dissemination events, exhibitions, and forums) means. According to the preliminary design of the policy, infrastructural and programmatic means may be managed bureaucratically, i.e., by formal institutions, or democratically, i.e., by stakeholders.

[10-8] There are infrastructural and programmatic means in the design of the policy that promote a fairer distribution of epistemic resources, mostly managed by local stakeholders. Score higher the more influence local stakeholders have in the management of these means according to the preliminary policy.

[7-5] There are infrastructural and programmatic means in the design of the policy that promote a fairer distribution of epistemic resources, mostly managed bureaucratically. Score higher the more influence local stakeholders have in the management of these means according to the preliminary policy.

[4-2] There are either infrastructural or programmatic means in the design of the policy that promote a fairer distribution of epistemic resources. Score higher if most of these means are managed by local stakeholders’ collectives.

[1] There are no means in the design of the policy that promote a fairer distribution of epistemic resources.

23) Epistemic capabilities (ex-post)

To what extent does the proposed policy advance fairer distributions of epistemic capabilities? And to what extent does this distribution aid local communities?

To advance distributive epistemic justice, epistemic capabilities need to be fairly distributed among stakeholders. Epistemic capabilities are substantial freedoms that stakeholders possess to pursue ends that they value in the epistemic arena. As an illustration, epistemic capabilities include (but are not limited to) the ability to search and acquire information and knowledge, avoid false beliefs, make epistemic contributions, gain credibility, and learn specific methodologies. Individuals may be differently able to convert epistemic resources into actions that advance their epistemic ends. This is why a focus on capabilities is required to complement the assessment of the distribution of resources. As a process indicator, the scoring system does not evaluate the effects of the policy on the distribution of epistemic capabilities (that would make it an outcome indicator). Instead, the scoring is based on how the preliminary design of the policy, either explicitly or implicitly, addresses issues of distribution of epistemic capabilities. Given our preference for a ‘prioritarian’ principle, a higher score is given when the design of the policy describes mechanisms that promote egalitarian distributions that deviate from the principle of equity only to benefit local communities. We take local management of these mechanisms as a proxy for such deviation. Mechanisms to advance a fair distribution of epistemic capabilities may be infrastructural (e.g., free access to repositories, libraries, and media) or programmatic (e.g., dissemination events,

exhibitions, and forums). These mechanisms may be managed bureaucratically, i.e., by formal institutions, or democratically, i.e., by stakeholders.

[10-8] There are infrastructural and programmatic mechanisms in the design of the policy that promote a fairer distribution of epistemic capabilities, mostly managed by local stakeholders. Score higher the more influence local stakeholders have in the management of these mechanisms.

[7-5] There are infrastructural and programmatic mechanisms in the design of the policy that promote a fairer distribution of epistemic capabilities, mostly managed bureaucratically. Score higher if local stakeholders have more influence in the management of these mechanisms.

[4-2] There are either infrastructural or programmatic mechanisms in the design of the policy that promote a fair distribution of epistemic capabilities. Score higher if most of these mechanisms are managed by local stakeholders' collectives.

[1] There are no mechanisms in place that promote a fair distribution of epistemic capabilities.